

3d-Quasi-Optical Ray-Tracing for the Odin Radiometer

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ABSTRACT:

We describe the Odin radiometer optical layout and the 3-dimensional CAD system developed to define and analyze the system. Both the mechanical and optical design were done within the same CAD environment using a custom plug-in software for Quasi-Optical analysis and ray tracing. Odin has a complex optical layout with three dimensional beam foldings and a large number of optical elements. The optical/mechanical CAD system allows control over the definition of mirror and lens surfaces, as well as the mechanical support structure and apertures, bringing all elements into a single 3-dimensional model.

Odin Optical Layout:

The optical layout for the Odin radiometer is based on the prototype version described by Ordell[1], with some improvements introduced for the flight version. Odin has five receivers: four of which are submillimeter and one is millimeter wave. The four submillimeter mixers are arranged in cross-polarized pairs. Each pair looks at two Martin-Puplett diplexers, one for LO injection and one for side band rejection. Because of the arrangement of the grids in the diplexer tower, each mixer beam takes a different path through the diplexer. As a result, there are eight tuning mechanisms which move the right-angled roof-top mirrors that perform the beam polarization rotation. In Figure 1a, one can see how the beam comes out of one level of the diplexer tower and then is folded back into the next level by two mirrors. Those folding mirrors are profiled in order to contain or "re-collimate" the beam. In all, the beam goes through four focussing elements before being sent off to the telescope secondary mirror.

All the mirrors in Odin are off-axis ellipsoid mirrors in order to control aberrations [2]. In Figures 1a and b, the rings shown on the mirror surfaces are the physical locations where the incoming Gaussian beam intersects the surface of the mirror at edge tapers of 5dB, 15dB, 25dB, and 35dB. The CAD drawing of the mirror is accurately drawn with the surface profile we expect to manufacture, and we have used this to verify the mirrors by comparing the drawing to mechanical depth measurements of the mirror surfaces.

After the diplexer tower there is yet another mechanism: A simple rotating Dicke switch. Both sides of the Dicke switch are used such that one pair of mixers is viewing the astronomical source while the other pair is looking at the internal calibration source. We have a choice of calibration sources: one warm, and two cold. The two cold are simply looking directly at the cold sky (not through the telescope). We achieve this through one final mechanism which is a rotating switch mirror, making ten mechanisms in all in Odin. The mirror mounted on this last mechanism is also a profiled surface, and the axis

of rotation of the mirror is such that we don't introduce any aberrations. That is, we only reflect the beam to the designed beam reflection angle.

The 119GHz beam comes into the Dicke switch via a dichroic where it joins the submillimeter beam from the bottom level of the diplexer. In Figure 1b, the Gaussian beam for the 119GHz channel is drawn as a 3-dimensional surface of revolution. This method is useful for ensuring sufficient clearance throughout the optical path. For example, in Figure 1b, a mirror in the calibration chain has its bottom corner bitten off such that there is a clear path for the sky beam when the switch mirror selects that position.

Lenses with linear matching grooves

The 119GHz channel has two lenses in the optical path. In other parts of the optical design, off-axis ellipsoid mirrors have been used because they transform the phase front radius of an incident beam into the desired output beam with a spherical phase front radius and Gaussian amplitude distribution [2]. The corresponding surface of refraction which performs the same transformation is a cartesian oval [5]. On Odin, we have used single surface lenses in which the first surface is spherical and matched to the phase radius of the incident beam. There is therefore no transformation at the first surface. The second surface is a cartesian oval.

In order to reduce reflections at the surface of the lens, a matching layer of grooves has been machined into the surfaces of the lens. Circular grooves have the disadvantage of a mismatch where they do not line up, or exactly cross, the polarization vector of the receiver [6]. This effect can be reduced by using linear matching grooves that line up with the linearly polarized receiver beam. Machining of grooves into the lens surface was done by a Computer Numerically Controlled milling machine (see Figure 2). The program used to control the machine was produced by the Quasi-Optics plug-in software as a text output file containing the required Heidenheim control language syntax.

Quasi-Optics Software:

The Quasi-Optical analysis was achieved using a 3-dimensional Quasi-Optical ray tracing program developed by the author. The program currently runs as a plug-in to AutoCAD™ [3], or other "AutoCAD fluent" software such as IntelliCAD98™ [4]. The plug-in performs the Quasi-Optic calculations in addition to drawing the entities. In the Odin drawings, all the beam envelopes shown are drawn to the 35dB edge taper of a Gaussian beam. These are hyperbolae, and in the case where a tube represents the beam, this is a surface of revolution formed by the hyperbola. For clarity, the 3-d beam is not shown everywhere because it would make a cluttered drawing, however they are in the drawing (some of them are on "frozen layers"). This three dimensional ray tracing has proven to be extremely useful in spotting areas where we might otherwise have truncated the beam. Odin has such a compact design with many beam foldings in all directions that it would be difficult to keep track of everything without a 3-d ray tracing.

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Figure 1: Isometric views of the Odin radiometer. The 119GHz beam is drawn as a 3-dimensional surface of revolution bounded by a hyperbola which is the 35dB edge taper envelope of a Gaussian beam.

Figure 2: A teflon lens with linear matching grooves machined into the profiled surface. The lens surface is a surface of revolution formed by a cartesian oval.